

A STUDY ON INDIAN STOCK MARKET – BEFORE AND AFTER COVID – 19

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ABSTRACT:

The Coronavirus outbreak, which has been declared a global health emergency, had a wide range of consequences, ranging from ecological to economic. Since the first recorded incidence in China in December 2019, over 80 countries have jointly registered over 90,000 cases. The virus's influence is being felt on the worldwide market, with one of the world's largest economies at the epicentre of the unique Coronavirus outbreak. Closer to home, the Indian stock market has taken a beating as a result of its geographical and economic proximity to China. This study discusses the Indian stock market, before and after COVID – 19. Various aspects pertaining to the stock market trends are highlighted here in this study.

Keywords: *Stock Market, India, COVID – 19*

I. INTRODUCTION:

The unprecedented COVID19 epidemic has put the world in peril and shifted the global landscape in unanticipated ways. The SARSCoV2 virus, which caused the COVID19 outbreak, first appeared in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, in December 2019, and quickly spread around the world. This pandemic is not just a global health crisis, but it is also a major global economic downturn. The economic activity of several countries is abruptly halted as strict quarantine measures are enacted to battle an unknown disease. Transportation across countries is restricted, if not outright forbidden, causing global economic activity to suffer. Most crucially, terror among consumers and businesses has stopped them from engaging in their customary purchase habits, resulting in market abnormality. Uncertainty and risk are being created as a result of the epidemic, which is having a significant economic impact on both advanced and rising economies such as the United States, Spain, Italy, Brazil, and India.

The financial market has reacted with spectacular movement and has been badly affected as a result of this. Economic instability associated to COVID19 has had a considerable impact on the financial sector, which encompasses both stock and bond markets. As a consequence of the outbreak, the oil price has decreased substantially, but the gold price has increased dramatically. This pandemic is referred to by Firzli (2020) as "the larger financial crisis." Businesses are heavily leveraged in many nations, weak corporations are further destabilised, and corporate debt is at an all-time high. As a result of the pandemic, the global financial market risk has increased significantly (Zhang et al., 2020). Fear and uncertainty have caused enough losses for investors. For example, the global stock market lost nearly US Dollars around six trillion in one week from February 24 to February 28 as a result of the pandemic's impact (Ozili & Arun, 2020). Since the pandemic outbreak, the market value of standard & poor 500 indices has dropped by around thirty percent. According to Azimili (2020), increased uncertainty affects the required rate of return and, as a result, the current market value of stocks.

The pandemic's devastating impacts extended to emerging economies over time. When we examine the emerging economy's financial industry, we get a grim picture, as this economy has been hit the hardest by the drop in oil prices. The emergence of the pandemic has made this situation even more urgent. Leading emerging markets including Brazil, Russia, and Mexico have tightened mobility restrictions, forcing emerging economies to fall into a 1% recession by 2020. The Coronavirus pandemic in South Korea caused KOSPI to go below 1,600 for first time in its history after ten years (So, 2020). Higher COVID19 uncertainty leads to greater stock return volatility in China (Leduc & Liu, 2020). On March 22, 2020, In order to reduce epidemics, the Indian government imposed a Janata Curfew and a confinement programme to protect social distancing practises. Following the government's implementation of such a lockdown policy, several commercial operations were unexpectedly suspended. As a result of the worldwide market disruption, India's financial market has seen significant volatility (Raja Ram, 2020). As a result of the global economic system's crisis, the Indian stock market is suffering severe volatility. The pandemic has taken a toll on it as well. The upcoming sections gives the stock market scenario before and after COVID – 19.

II. STOCK MARKET BEFORE COVID -19

Various research addressed in this section illustrate that any worldwide crisis has always had an impact on the stock market, even before the commencement of the epidemic. Corporate governance is a major contributor to the global financial crisis. According to Deepak & Lalwani Idnani's research in 2015. According to Kumar & Vashisht research in 2019, countries with fewer international currency reserves in proportion to their current account deficits sustained more losses during the 2008 economic crisis.

The impact of crises on stock market volatility was discovered by Rastogi in his research. They conducted research on the stock market's volatility index before and after the crisis. The study's finding was that the impact is heavily influenced by the volatility of various countries. Siddiqui also looked at the effects of the financial crisis on India and China's economies. The results suggest that the crisis had an influence on emerging market growth, employment, and trade. The economic crisis of 2008 was the greatest recession in the last century, as per his article "Learning from Lehman: A Year Later."(Rastogi et. al., 2014)

III. STOCK MARKET POST COVID – 19:

The Sensex on the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and the Nifty on the National Stock Exchange (NSE) are the two primary stock indices in India (NSE). According to the Bombay Stock Exchange, the Sensex index decreased to 13.2 percent on March 23, 2020. After the Harshad Mehta Scandal broke on April 28, 1991, it was their highest-charting single (Mandal, 2020). Similarly, over that time period, the Nifty has plummeted approximately 29%. COVID19's influence on the Indian stock market has been dubbed a "black swan event" by some economists, referring to the occurrence of a highly unexpected event with catastrophic consequences. As a result of the government's lockdown strategy, factories have cut their labour force as well as output levels, disrupting the supply chain. People restrict their consumption patterns as a result of the uncertainty that exists among mankind, resulting in demand-side shock. According to studies, the last pandemic merely had an effect on the demand chain. However, pandemic has had an impact on both the demand and supply chains.

In March 2020, the market capitalisation of listed companies on the NSE and the BSE both

decreased by over 20%. The financial market experienced a continuous decline in stock values throughout the month of March 2020. Singh and Neog (2020) enlisted the trend of the Sensex and NIFTY, in which it is observed that the decrease is more rapid from the first week of March 2020, in agreement with these declining patterns of the Indian stock market. The survey also found that a loss of around three lakh crore had nearly entirely disrupted the economic, housing, and banking industries. The influence of the COVID-19 shutdown period on the Indian stock market was explored by Alam et al. (2020). According to their findings, the public panicked during the epidemic before the lockdown, and aberrant returns decreased as a result of the anxiety. The public, on the other hand, acquired faith throughout the lockdown, as seen by the positive and significant abnormal returns.

IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS:

The impact of the corona virus on the stock market was measured using the share prices of the top 20 businesses listed on the National Stock Exchange (NSE). The information was gathered on a weekly basis, and the closing prices of the stocks were considered. Various share prices, such as the opening, closing, high, and low values, are reported for a given week. Authors (Jindal et. al., 2020) closing prices were used since they represent investor sentiment as well as the impact of major news events on stock prices.

Name of Comp any	Date (Weekly data: Year 2020)														
	1/1 3	1/2 0	1/2 7	2/3	2/1 0	2/1 7	2/2 4	3/2	3/9	3/1 6	3/2 3	3/3 0	4/6	4/1 3	4/1 7
Reliance Industries	15 81	15 22	13 83	14 34	14 88	14 86	13 29	12 71	11 05	10 18	10 66	10 77	12 20	12 24	12 24
TCS	22 19	21 83	21 65	21 37	21 84	21 57	20 00	21 16	18 06	17 97	18 25	16 54	17 66	18 06	18 06
HUL*	20 60	20 74	20 75	21 60	22 55	22 48	21 75	21 89	20 33	20 52	21 41	21 54	23 72	23 85	23 85
HDFC Bank	12 78	12 45	11 99	12 42	12 19	12 17	11 78	11 35	10 70	88 3	90 4	81 4	92 5	91 0	91 0
HDFC	24 54	24 51	22 68	24 06	24 02	23 70	21 76	21 09	20 67	17 54	17 54	15 00	17 03	16 81	16 81
Bharti Airtel	50 0	52 4	49 7	53 9	56 5	54 6	52 4	51 9	49 2	46 3	44 9	42 4	48 9	50 2	50 2
Infosys	76 8	78 3	78 0	77 7	78 6	79 7	73 2	73 9	64 2	58 5	65 3	58 6	63 6	62 9	62 9
ICICI Bank	53 2	53 4	50 5	53 6	54 6	54 7	49 7	48 6	44 7	34 6	34 0	28 7	34 3	37 6	37 6
ITC	24 0	23 8	21 9	21 3	20 8	20 7	19 8	18 2	16 2	17 6	16 3	17 8	18 5	18 8	18 8

Kotak Mahindra	1698	1643	1648	1653	1681	1686	1620	1631	1470	1262	1399	1141	1273	1186	1186
SBI	318	324	303	321	319	328	303	271	242	210	196	176	188	193	193
Asian Paints	1830	1787	1755	1859	1877	1842	1798	1877	1798	1743	1604	1521	1651	1756	1756
Nestle *	15440	15756	15525	16328	16357	16540	15779	16429	14992	14146	15109	15105	16840	17324	17324
Maruti Suzuki	7520	7128	6813	6972	6914	6758	6283	6446	5839	5079	4646	4012	5327	5505	5505
Avenue Supermarts *	1991	1949	2072	2287	2408	2463	2324	2242	2101	1916	2080	2067	2393	2212	2212
Bajaj Finance	4232	4195	4276	4654	4782	4880	4466	4226	3953	2952	2542	2208	2552	2308	2308
Axis Bank	740	737	705	748	737	744	697	658	569	428	360	325	420	479	479
Larsen	1304	1359	1287	1299	1295	1281	1188	1159	1051	865	837	775	813	933	933
HCL Tech	599	608	591	608	622	608	534	566	493	445	431	406	469	455	455
Sun Pharma	455	448	423	431	419	405	373	401	384	365	338	376	454	457	457

Table 1: Share price of top 20 companies in NSE week wise from 13 January to 17 April (Jindal et. al., 2020)

On looking at the first and final closing prices in the table above, it can be seen that the share prices of most of the companies have decreased. However, the stock prices of corporations like HUL, Nestle, and Avenue Supermarts have risen. This could be because the demand for essential supplies has surged dramatically during the lockdown. As a result of the lockdown in so many countries and people choosing a work-from-home strategy, energy consumption, transport, and project professionals in several industries such as IT and infrastructure has declined considerably.

The graph 1 below highlights the same aspect:

Graph 1 – Percentage change of price in selected companies stocks (Jindal et. al., 2020)

On calculating overall volume of different industries, the graph 2 below shows the trend:

Graph 2 – Average Volume

On taking the data from five organisations at a time to understand the shift in the situation. It is estimated the percentage change in volume as a function of time. With few exceptions, the value of share prices is on a downward trend, as shown in the graphs above.

V. CONCLUSION:

COVID-19 has a different influence on different industries. According to the data, the share prices of most of the companies on the top 20 list of the NSE 50 have decreased dramatically over time. As a result, COVID-19 has had a significant impact on India's stock market. However, the aggregate volume exchanged has increased over time. As a result, more money is being invested in the market, demonstrating that people believe in the Indian economy. Stock prices plunged approximately thirty percent in the March quarter, according to a recent Business Line article, while high-net-worth individuals (HNIs) went on a buying spree at the same time.

The stock market was severely impacted by the previous virus's impact. During the SARS

outbreak in 2003, the share values of the information systems and communication industries fell by around fourteen percentage and twenty six percentage, respectively. As a result of the IKA virus, the market lost almost thirteen percent in 66 sessions in 2015. The market plunged by 6% to 13% six years ago as a result of the EBOLA fear. The findings of the study contribute to a better understanding of how stocks react to extraordinary occurrences in emerging markets. The findings demonstrate the importance of knowledge in influencing the stock market in developing countries like India.

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